

Data Analytics and Machine Learning Workshop Evaluation Form

26 responses

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What is your designation?

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26 responses

- Student (BSc, MSc, PhD candidates)
- Researcher/Faculty (including postdocs)
- Industrial Practitioner
- Faculty/Doctoral student
- Staff (Senior Administrator)

How long have you been practicing?

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26 responses

- 0 to 3 years
- 3 to 5 years
- 5 to 8 years
- 8 to 12 years
- 12 to 15 years
- more than 15 years

Workshop content covered useful materials

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Workshop content was practical to my needs and interests

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26 responses

Workshop content was well organized

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26 responses

Workshop content was well paced

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26 responses

Workshop content was presented at the right level

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26 responses

Workshop presenters presented quality visual aids and handouts

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26 responses

How will you rate knowledge of presenters at the workshop?

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26 responses

How will you rate presentation style of presenters at the workshop?

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26 responses

Did presenters cover topics clearly?

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26 responses

Did presenters facilitate interactions among participants?

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26 responses

How could this conference be improved?

26 responses

Increase number of days. Content was rich and can be dissected and covered effectively over 2-3 days

It should be more than a day's programme.

Increase number of days

To include data collection

The duration should be increased

More hand-on sessions

Yes. More days, specifically 2 to 3 days. One day is not enough

The days should be increased to accomodate the practical nature of the workshop and the material been presented

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More practical and hands on

Having it more than one day

Based on topics covered it should have been at least 3 days workshop

A more practical session would help but it was well organized with relevant content.

An improved drive (storage) coordination to ensure all participants have easy access to material

It couldn't extended to 3 days to give presenters more time to touch on their topics

You could make it a two-day workshop so as to cover all areas.

Nothing to think of right now.

The conference should be done over 3days period

Should be a 2 day event rather than a day.

By extending the number of days

It could be spaced between multiple days

The conference could be improved through the following suggested means: 1. Add more practical basic management tools such as excel, stats, spss. Data collection means should be add to the process. Many institution lacks the means to source accurate data for use.

State-of-the-art presentation (What, How, When) and its applications

Content should be shared early to selected and confirm participants

Additional day or two to cover more areas especially the use of softwares for the workshop would be appreciated

More time should be allocated for practise

Provide any other comments or suggestions here

26 responses

NA

N/A

Generally it's was a good programme.

WhatsApp group should be created for networking

If the duration be extended to cover data collection

Well done

The workshop duration was too short hence facilitators could not do much.

More practical hands-on

Generally it was a very good ...I appreciate the opportunity given.

I suggest a more practical session with the days extended to at least 3 days intensively.

Should be made a two day workshop

More days are required for meaningful impact

None

This workshop should have been a minimum of two days. The first two session's (Data cleaning and data virtualization) could have been held on the first day and the session on machine learning on the second with practical interaction (where the presenter generate the codes alongside the audience and not a pre written code as we had).

A bigger room

I believe time was a constrain that hinder the presenters to deliver their full content

All materials should be distributed early enough for participants to go through before the workshop starts.

The workshop was very much needed

the duration for the conference was too short. such a very good impactful conference should be given enough time/duration

More time for further practical/hands-on training would be great

I will suggest an entire day dedicated to a particular topic

The numbers for the workshop should be extended to give way for practical tutoring on the use of the data analytics tools.

There should be some transportation allowances for participants as well. The workshop in general is a success and impactful.

Regular workshops on subject matter

Alert on future workshops, organizers should use early hours to prepare the participant if there are any app's installations or labs information regarding the presentation.

Organizers should consider having the conference in 2 or more days instead of 1. This is to give more time for practise.

Overall, how would you rate this workshop?

26 responses

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